

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

PREREQUISITES AND WORLDVIEW FOUNDATIONS OF HERODOTUS' "HISTORY"

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the analysis of the prerequisites for the creation of the first historical work in the history of mankind - "History" by Herodotus. The importance of the works of the school - logographers - who for the first time departed from the traditional and poetic forms of presentation of historical events, is revealed. Special attention is paid to the role of Hecateus as a direct predecessor of Herodotus. The general worldview foundations of "History" in the context of intellectual and cultural development of ancient Greece are revealed.

Keywords: historical science, Ancient Greece, methodology of historical cognition, Ancient Greece, Herodotus, logographers, Hecataeus, worldview foundations, intellectual and cultural development of ancient Greece.

The development of science is always the work of its specific representatives. As already noted, in the 5th century BC, on the basis of already formed, albeit still spontaneous and naive, scientific and philosophical ideas about the cosmos, the first systematic works were created, the subject of which was the historical development of human society as its constituent part. The beginning of this process was Herodotus of Halicarnassus (about 484 - 425 B.C.), the author of the treatise "History" describing the Greek-Persian wars.

Why Herodotus in particular? Because his personality, his methods of selecting material and his work itself were the object of constant "hot" discussions, which began almost immediately after the appearance of the "History" and continue to this day. And assessments were given diametrically opposite - from the "father of lies", according to Aristotle, to the "father of history", according to the winged expression of Cicero, which has survived to our days.

Nevertheless, the process of formation of methodological foundations of historical science should begin with Herodotus.

Firstly, the very fact of constant discussions about his place and role in the formation of historical knowledge already testifies to the importance of the treatise "History". Insignificant works would not have been discussed so actively and for so long; they would have been soon forgotten.

Secondly, Herodotus' "History" is the first large and systematic work that has come down to us. From the predecessors of the "father of history" have survived only fragments that do not allow us to perform any serious analysis of their methodological approaches. Moreover, the extant fragments show that it is very difficult to classify their works as "historical". The work of Herodotus in this respect far surpasses everything that was written before him and what has been preserved. It opens a new page in the ancient Greek tradition of historiography. The historical narratives of Herodotus, and after him Thucydides, differed from both heroic epic and early ethnographic chronicles. From the epic - by the fact that they freed history from

myth; from the chronicles - by a fundamentally different scale of narration.[2, p. 7].

Thirdly, Herodotus is the first author known to us, who set the task of creating a universal (taking into account the concrete-historical conditions in which his work took place) history, rather than a description of individual polis or territories [3, p. 151]. His predecessors, judging by the surviving fragments, limited themselves to descriptions of events in the area where they lived.

Fourthly, it is with the "History" that a coherent and consistent tradition of historical science begins [7, p. 206]. Later historians wrote after Herodotus: where Herodotus finished his description, Thucydides continued it; where Thucydides finished his description, Xenophontes began it, etc.

Fifthly and finally, Herodotus' work itself had a great influence both on the development of historical science and on Greek culture in general. Knowledge of historical works became a necessary element of the general culture of the citizen of the polis. The works of the predecessors of the "father of history" in the field of historical descriptions (although some of them were preserved in some ancient libraries for quite a long time) almost no one read, except for a narrow circle of "specialists". And "History" was read constantly; people argued with it [6, p. 206]. Herodotus' views were discussed; they served as a starting point for further development of both the methodology of historical research and the ways and forms of description and presentation of historical events. In other words, Herodotus for the first time "incorporated" the primary elements of scientific and historical knowledge available to him into the Helladic culture, for which it was necessary to justify them on the basis of philosophical ideas already existing in it [5].

Thus, it is with the "History" that the formation of methodological foundations of historical science begins. To understand the scientific and methodological significance of this work it is necessary to analyse its worldview and theoretical foundations in comparison with the works of predecessors and to identify new and

enduring elements of scientific analysis that determine the ways of accumulation, selection, comprehension and presentation of material by Herodotus.

It is obvious that it was impossible to create at once such a voluminous, systematised and multifaceted in content work as the "Histories", relying only on myths and mythologised poetic sources. Indeed, Herodotus drew on the Ionian intellectual tradition as a whole. Although he was a Dorian, he wrote in the Ionian dialect, obviously following the tradition formed by his time: historical research should be created in the Ionian way [3, p. 209 - 211]. This is a valid connection of the "father of history" with his predecessors. But much more was what separated them.

Just as the first philosophical school in history emerged in Ionia (Miletus), the tradition of Ionian historiography, which can be defined as the first ancient historiographical school [7, pp. 209-211], was formed there several generations later. Its representatives - logographers - created prose works called "logos", which means "word", "story" [1, p. 458], representing an obvious step forward in comparison with the previous mythologically oriented poetry. In them, a fundamentally new view of previous historical narratives begins to take shape: myths are not rejected or discarded, but comprehended as their own "ancient history". (In this sense, they did not really sin against history, "since modern science of Antiquity is increasingly convinced that almost every hero of Greek myths really had a real prototype in the history of the II millennium BC.) Thus, most of the so-called historical myths really reflect (another question is how adequately) the historical situation of the Cretan-Mycenaean epoch" [8, p. 328 - 329]. In general, in this period of antiquity, the mythological tradition was treated as historical. Myths were perceived by the public consciousness not as fictions, but as "sacred history", which should be understood [ibid.] and accepted after the elimination of absolutely fantastic elements of the narrative. And the logographers began a rational reworking of the existing mythology, trying to build genealogical links between the demigod-heroes and the noble Greek surnames contemporary to them.

The pinnacle of logography is the work "Genealogy" by Hecataeus of Miletus (ca. 550 - 490 BC). Judging by the excerpts, its content consists, on the one hand, of purely geographical messages, on the other hand, of the mythological prahistory of Greece, from which the author also derives direct genealogical lines to himself and his contemporaries [3, p. 145]. However, its actual place in the formation of historical science is determined by other factors - Hecataeus not only systematised the works of predecessors-logographers, but also for the first time clearly formulated methodological approaches to the comprehension and presentation of historical data, actually leading the author beyond the limits of this tradition.

In "Genealogy" Hecataeus, following the already formed tradition, subjected to rationalistic criticism the ancient Greek mythology [7, p. 48], trying to discard the obviously fantastic elements and to highlight those elements of the narrative that could take place in reality.

However, this is only the first, but not the most important step in his work. Hecataeus then proceeds to a critical-rational reinterpretation of mythological narratives. And assessments of this significant component of his work vary. There is an opinion that Hecataeus has "elements of rationalistic criticism of myths" [4, p. 48]. However, in our opinion, his criticism of mythology is more profound.

In fact, it can be argued that Hecataeus realises this heuristic approach consistently and systematically. Scientists belonging to his generation, proceeded from the general world outlook developed by Ionian philosophy a century before, and on their basis considered the natural world and human society [3, p. 151], as well as myths as evidence of "ancient history". And in the "Genealogy" all the basic principles of ancient historiography, on the basis of which the substantial "reworking" of mythology took place, are fully present [ibid., p. 104 - 107]:

1. any myth is somehow based on real events. Consequently, *by means of its rational comprehension it is possible to obtain a historical account by eliminating fantastic elements;*

2. since myth is a distortion of real events, special methods were required to eliminate such inconsistencies: *syncretism of motifs and its antipode - duplication of motifs* (renaming the heroes of alien myths into "our own" ones; combining two myths into one);

3. *secularisation of gods* - a part of "minor" gods turned into mortals;

4. *chronological fixation of events: on the basis of the method of generations and the method of synchronicities* to determine the approximate time of the events, the counting was done in reverse order, at the rate of three generations in a hundred years;

5. *etymologisation* - non-Greek words were broken down into similar Greek word roots to determine their true meaning.

Hecataeus, of course, could not simply "discard" the established narrative tradition and had to reckon with it. However, he subjected it to a rather sharp, principled criticism. In his interpretation, the earlier works in this field are a "negative example", which he rejects [9, p.30]. As a result, Hecataeus "breaks away" from his predecessors-logographers. He makes a clear leap in the development of the existing historiography, aiming, on the basis of rational comprehension, to find the truth in mythological narratives. As a result of such transformation of methods of comprehension of myths and presentation of the obtained results, Hecataeus creates "polemical and reasoned stories" [ibid., p. 24].

Hecataeus also deserves great merit in the formation of the primary methodological principles of the choice of the material to be presented and the construction of the narrative. He formulates the first in European historiography theoretical judgement of a general nature, which gives a lot for understanding the peculiarities of the ancient Greek approach to history. "Genealogy" begins with the words: "Thus says Hecataeus of Miletus: I write this as it seems true to me, for the stories of the Hellenes are manifold and ridiculous, as it seems to me" (Hecataeus. Fr. 1 Jacoby) [quoted in 7, p.

196]. In this fragment it is absolutely necessary to emphasise several substantial aspects, which reflect both the general characteristics of the cultural tradition of the West and the specificity of the ancient Greek understanding of the historical quest.

Firstly, the authorial, individual beginning is clearly expressed - at the very beginning of the narrative the author puts his own name. This is a manifestation of individualism, the "competitive spirit", which is generally extremely strong in all spheres of ancient Greek culture and is an essential element of the civilizational tradition of the West, as noted earlier.

Secondly, Hecataeus defines the search for truth as his main task, rather than a mere recounting of events. He considered himself obliged to write only what he himself assesses as true. However, at the same time, he clearly indicates the subjectivity of his own opinion and, therefore, allows for the possibility of other points of view.

Thirdly, a sharply critical attitude towards his predecessors is unambiguously recorded. For him there is nothing self-evident. Hecataeus strives to follow the original understanding of history - "to investigate, to examine" - and therefore rejects the preceding tradition, criticises and ridicules it [7, p. 196]. (And this initial "harsh" criticality towards the material under study will later be continued by Thucydides.) It should be noted, however, that these methodological guidelines stated by Hecataeus were not fully implemented by him - in fact, he performed rationalisation of mythological stories [3, pp. 145 - 147], rather than outlining real historical events.

Nevertheless, the merit of Hecataeus in the emergence of historical science is undoubted - he made a qualitative leap in the development of ancient Greek historiography. Having as predecessors mythologists-historiographers, relying on their tradition of pre-scientific mythologically oriented description and critically comprehending it, he wrote an integral, complete and reasoned work - a real "proto-scientific narrative" [9, p. 24]. Thus, the necessary prerequisite for the emergence of scientific historical works proper was created.

Therefore, the fact that Herodotus repeatedly called Hecataeus his predecessor [7, p. 194], is quite reasonable and natural.

(It should be noted that this evolutionary path (mythology - protoscience - science) in the ancient Greek (Ionian) historical tradition was passed quite quickly - within two generations. An undoubted positive influence, which accelerated it, was the Ionian natural philosophy, already existing for a century, within the framework of which many methodological principles of both mythology criticism and cognition of the Cosmos were developed).

As already noted, the earliest works of Greek prose were called "logos," which means "word," "story," in the sense of form of presentation - a prose work as opposed to poetic forms. Herodotus also uses this term in relation to the "History", denoting by it the parts of his work possessing thematic unity, as well as the whole work [1, p. 458]. As a result, the meaning of the term changes significantly - it acquires a meaning, which it retains in the future - "logos" is "knowledge",

and knowledge is holistic. Therefore, Herodotus begins his book with what Hecataeus completed - he immediately focuses on building a comprehensive (if possible) picture of historical events, the first of the extant ones.

Before proceeding to the study of the methodological foundations of historical cognition underlying Herodotus' "History", it is necessary to make some explanations. Each scientist-historian (as well as any scientist - representative of other fields of scientific knowledge) - is based on his own (in the sense - not absolutely identical to others) understanding of the ways of description and explanation, justification and proof, construction and organisation of the knowledge obtained by him. Even if scientists belong to the same scientific school, adhere in principle to the same research methodology, certain differences in the interpretation of the obtained results will still occur. As a result, a model of the historical process is created, reflecting it in a certain way. This model may be more or less accurate, but it can never coincide with real history in all its diversity. Since the historical process cannot be repeated, it cannot be reproduced (unlike an experiment in classical natural science), there is no fundamental possibility of verifying the truth of the entire historical account. Written history as a result of the work of a scientist-historian is a synthesis of the objectively occurring historical process, which is partially represented in the preserved factual material, selected in a certain way (absolutely everything cannot be taken into account), the way of description and interpretation of this material. The scholar-historian, of course, can be aware of and take into account his own subjectivity, trying to minimise it with the help of certain procedures of verification of historical data. But, in general, every author is convinced that, in general, in the basic, essential and necessary characteristics, patterns and processes, the real course of history (or its individual components) was exactly as he described it. This conviction is due to the fact that the description of the course of history is based on certain concrete-historical foundations of science, developed before or during the lifetime of the scientist, comprehended and perceived by him as true. It is on their basis that various pictures of reality are modelled, which are interpreted as a complete and accurate reflection of objective reality as a whole or of some of its components (in this case, the history of human society). It is accepted to distinguish at least three main components of the foundations of science: ideals and norms of research, scientific picture of the world and philosophical foundations of science [8], each of which also has an internal structure. As a result, in order to understand the sources and reasons for the emergence of a particular variant of historiography, it is necessary to analyse the existing worldview and methodological attitudes and principles of a particular author and identify their real content, which may differ from what he himself states.

A detailed study of Herodotus' heritage in this regard is of paramount importance, since all subsequent works of historical scholars were necessarily created correlatively to the first "History".

As noted earlier, Herodotus' work was not only the first example of a systematic historical narrative. Its appearance was also a significant cultural phenomenon - Herodotus' work was read and discussed not only by politicians and historians, but also by ordinary citizens of the polis. "History" entered the ancient Greek culture and was preserved in it during the following centuries. This fact shows that Herodotus' ideas about the world, realised in his work, corresponded to the worldview of his epoch [5], were understandable and consonant with the mindset of the citizens of Greek city-states. In the worldview of Herodotus eclectically combined several essential components.

The most important of them is the system of ideas about the world, formed within the framework of the Ionian intellectual tradition, which was mentioned earlier. Ionian natural philosophy, having begun to characterise the world as a purely natural, natural system from the side of its essence, quality, gradually passed to the description of general regularities of its mode of existence. And by the time of Herodotus' birth, general philosophical provisions on the unity of existence had been formulated. The eternal, constantly changing Cosmos was represented as a harmonious unity of all its parts (levels of organisation) - mega-, macro- and microcosms: the Universe, the earthly world and man. Uniform, general regularities constituted the essence of the world. This initial orientation was strengthened by the philosophy of Heraclitus - the whole is not the sum of parts; cognition of the whole is not equal to cognition of its parts. The general manifests itself in multiple phenomena that illustrate and concretise it, but do not change its essence. And this orientation to the general, to the integrity, to a single historical process, even to the detriment of accuracy, to the detriment of details, is consistently realised in the work of the "father of history".

Herodotus' worldview also contained elements of mythological worldview, which historically preceded philosophy. Despite his critical attitude to the classical mythological tradition, it generally appears to be something reliable. The endeavour to rationally comprehend and revise it was aimed at extracting some real knowledge. As a result, constant reference to mythology with necessity led to the preservation of certain features of mythological worldview in Herodotus' worldview, in particular, anthropocentrism [35, p. 157 - 158].

Herodotus is a sincere believer and at the same time a figure of Greek enlightenment of the V century BC. [Ibid. p.42], orientated on facts and building his inferences on them. This initial contradiction leads to the duality in understanding the place and role of the gods in the world. The world exists in itself. Gods are not abstract supernatural beginnings; they are material. Therefore, there are limits to the possibility of their interference in people's lives. They can establish some laws, the violation of which is punished - "for grave wrongs follow from the gods and grave punishments" [ibid, p. 39], but this applies only to humanity as a whole. In relation to specific people, the gods behave quite humanly: they are envious, dishonest, etc.

A significant component of Herodotus' worldview is also certain natural scientific knowledge, primarily in the field of geography. And this knowledge could differ from the existing in his time and be less reliable. Thus, the lands described in the "History" seemed to him significantly smaller than they actually were. "Herodotus protests against Hecataeus' assertion that Asia is equal in size to Europe. This statement, in his opinion, is absolutely ridiculous, for Europe is many times larger than Asia and with Libya (Africa) taken together" [ibid., p. 144].

And one more feature of the worldview of the author of the "History", following from the place of his birth and formation as a person, should be noted. Being a Hellene, Herodotus was born and grew up in Halicarnassus as a subject of the Persian power [8, p. 230 - 231]. Being on the border of two civilisations and belonging to both at the same time, he could state the views of each side on the events described in the "History".

The first historical work in the intellectual tradition of mankind was created on the basis of the above-mentioned ideas about the world.

The leitmotif of Herodotus' work was the history of the Greco-Persian wars. But in reality, the goal was much larger. In the famous introduction to his work, the author defines its theme as follows: "This is an account of Herodotus of Halicarnassus' research, [presented] so that time would not erase from memory all that was done by people, and also so that the glory of great and surprising deeds done by part Hellenes and part barbarians would not fade away, which concerns both everything else and the reason why war arose between them" [1, p. 469].

The phrase "which concerns both everything else" fundamentally expands the boundaries of the purpose of Herodotus' work, turning it, in fact, into a universal history. This universality is realised by him in several directions:

1. *in a historical context*, as events are described starting from the "beginning", i.e. from the mythological prehistory;

2. *in geographical context* - events occurring on the territory of all known lands of that time are described;

3. *ethnographic* (in modern terminology), since the task is to describe all the peoples who inhabited these lands;

4. *in a cognitive, substantive context* - Herodotus endeavours to "collect" and record all the information describing the life of the known humanity in the above-mentioned aspects.

It is obvious that Herodotus set himself the goal and tasks of super-scale, but they were realised. And his "History" took a worthy place not only as a historical work, but also as the first significant phenomenon of this type, organically integrated into the ancient Greek culture.

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